

DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING CAPACITY IN 5-6-YEARS OLD CHILDREN.

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Annotation: This article discusses the psychological development of 5-6 year old children's thinking ability and the improvement of its activity in children's psyche, i.e. psychology, and provides theoretical information.

Key words: child, thinking ability, conversation, giving questions, gene.

The development of cognitive capabilities in many ways follows the same principles. Robert Fisher is a leading expert in developing children's thinking skills, says that thinking is not a natural function like sleeping, walking and talking. Thinking, he stresses, needs to be developed, and people do not necessarily become wiser as they become older. Some children are lucky because they learn crucial thinking skills from their parents or other people. This work especially well when parents take the child seriously, engage them in meaningful conversations, inspire their imaginations, ask them questions that get them to think and so forth. The main reason is why, parents can know their children's thinking capability by asking questions which are related to thinking skills. Meanwhile, other children are less lucky as they do not have such a nurturing environment that fosters their cognitive development. However, both children from brain-friendly families and others who comes from less supportive contexts, will profit significantly from a teaching methods that takes the development of their thinking skills seriously.

The philosopher Matthew Lipman noticed a lack of reasoning skills in many children, and started a movement to involve children in philosophy, an approach that has spread to many countries of the world. He used the following metaphor to stress the need to systematically develop a child's thinking skills: when we compare a car mechanic with an average person who could never repair their own car, the difference is not that the car mechanic knows how to use tools such as a hammer, a screwdriver, pliers or a wrench. Most average people know how to do that too, yet they would fail hopelessly if they were to try to repair their car engine. What's diverse between them and the car mechanic is not the knowledge of how

to use a hammer, a screwdriver or a wrench. What the car mechanic knows, and what average people do not, is how to sequence the use of these tools in a way that leads to the planned outcome. The car mechanic knows what they are doing, and why they are doing it; and when what they are doing does not give them the planned outcome, they persevere trying to come up with alternative strategies that are bound to lead to eventual success. To sum up, the development of thinking ability of 5-6-years old children depends on children's genes and conversations between kids and their parents.

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